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Natālija Abrola

ORIGINS AND PROLIFERATION OF INDIC SCIENCES IN LATVIA

Introduction

A thread of this study emerged with the translation of a hymn in the Rigveda X mandala into Latvian by famous Latvian poet of the beginning of 20th century – Rainis (birth name: Jānis Krišjānis Pliekšāns (1865–1929)). This hymn was published in 1921 by Rainis in the collection of poems *Restless Heart. Songs from All Over the World*¹. One of the first hymns in this collection is “The Beginning of Things”², which, in its essence, is a cosmogonic type of hymn – one of the most renown hymns of the Rigveda – depicts the poet’s interest in cosmogony and orient.

This vague thread commenced the investigation of Indic sciences in Latvia. The current research traces the origins and proliferation of Indic sciences in Latvia within a time span from the end of the 19th century and, due to its limited scope, only to the 1940s. The research paper is divided into seven sections, including the introduction, which embraces the methodology and metadata sources, followed by brief insight into the origins of Indology in Europe embraced by Romanticism at the end of 18th century, as well as a look into the problematics of national awakening in India and Latvia. It will also provide an overview of early relevant

¹ Rainis, J. *Nemeerīga sirds. Dziesmas no visas pasaules*. Komanditsabedribas “Daile un Darbs” apgādē, 1921.

² *Ibid.*, pp. 9–10.

publications and societies operating in pre-World War II Latvia, discern new dimensions regarding Latvian poet Rainis and other litterateurs concerned with Orient. The analysis of interviews with people on yoga, ayurveda and Indian literature will be given at the conclusion.

To implement this study, following qualitative research methods have been applied, including archival research method, content analyses of semi-structured interviews with 8 respondents, analyses and synthesis. Only four interviews are relevant to this part of research. All the respondents have given a written consent to depositing of the interview audio recordings in the Archive of National Oral History³ (ANOH), as well as to use and publishing of the acquired data for the research purposes⁴.

Funds of Rainis and Rihards Rudzītis were investigated at Literature and Music Museum, as well as consultations and deciphering of postcards were performed by Rainis's researcher Dr. Gundega Grīnuma. Funds of Kārlis Egle were investigated at the Misiņš Library and the information gathered about the history of relevant Latvian societies during the pre-World War II period at the Latvian State Historical Archives (LSHA). Interviews with respondents were recorded from January 26 to March 14, 2018. This research has been partially funded by the State Culture Capital Foundation (SCCF).

1. Indology tide over Europe

The translation of Sanskrit texts into European languages was launched by the first Indologist – the French theologian – Abraham Hyacinthe Anquetil-Duperron (1731–1805), who finished translation of 50 Upanishads from Persian into Latin language in 1796⁵. Although German scholar Friedrich Wilhelm argues that the translation was done

³ The Project of National Oral History, hosted and conducted by Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, University of Latvia, Riga. Available at <http://www.dzivesstasts.lv/lv/free.php?main=502> (retrieved 09.11.2018).

⁴ The eight interviews are registered in the catalogue of ANOH: No. 4614–4620.

⁵ Ivbulis, V. *Indoeiropiešu dzimtenes meklējums*. Rīga: Zinātne, 2013, pp. 19–27.

in French⁶. This controversy requires clarification. Nevertheless, these translations reached Europe at the dawn of Romanticism, which was characterized by breaking the conservative codes of literary expressions of Neo-classicism and introducing the new waves of philosophical thought. The epoch of Romanticism and discovery of Eastern philosophies reaches Latvian intelligentsia and revolutionary writers and poets in the middle of 19th century. As stated by Lillian Furst, Romanticism did not commence homogenously at the beginning of the 19th century throughout Europe. Moreover, Furst asserts that Romanticism or rather pre-Romanticism originated in England by a poet Edward Young (1683–1765) in 1742, with publication of his poem “Night Thoughts”, and only later, around 1770–1790, France and Germany took it over⁷. Alongside the typical features manifested in Romanticism – expression of individualism, imagination and emotion –, Furst also indicates the notions of ‘original’, ‘genius’, ‘divine’, ‘grows’, ‘magician’ parallelly with the cult of sensibility, vague religious feelings, and the pantheistic approach of the unified cosmos⁸. Similarly, the movement of pre-Romanticism in Latvian literature was characterized by Pauls Daija with the expressions of self-reflection, where the individual is perceived as the centre of universe, and excitement about oriental and exotic motifs as well as mythology, all of it ignited by French philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712–1778) with his call ‘to return to the nature’. It is noteworthy to mention Rousseau’s disciple Johann Gottfried von Herder (1744–1803), who played a key role not only in German, but also in Latvian literary history by not only being an intermediary in bringing of Rousseau’s ideas to German adherents of *Sturm*

⁶ Wilhelm, F. The German Response to Indian Culture. *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, Vol. 81, No. 4, Sep.–Dec., 1961, pp. 395–405.

⁷ Furst, L. R. Romanticism in Historical Perspective. *Comparative Literature Studies* No. 5, 1968, pp. 115–120. Available at <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40467744> (retrieved 24.09.2018).

⁸ *Ibid.*, pp. 119–121.

und Drang movement^{9, 10}, but also by expressing interest in Latvian folk literature and the life of Latvian peasants. Hence, he published 11 of the Latvian songs in his book *Alte Volkslieder* in 1778¹¹. Wilhelm highlights the special role of Herder as it was particularly *Herder* who introduced Johann Wolfgang von Goethe (1749–1832) to Indian literature and philosophy. However, both of them alongside with the Schlegel brothers (Karl Wilhelm Friedrich (1772–1829) and August Wilhelm Schlegel (1767–1845)) were doubtlessly the pioneers and disseminators of Indology in Germany¹². Herder, in particular, who introduced Goethe to Latvian folksongs in 1770¹³. In 1802, German philosopher Arthur Schopenhauer (1788–1860) read the Latin translation of Upanishads, and thus the philosophy and values expressed therein became a significant source of inspiration in the construction of his philosophical ideas¹⁴. Subsequently, in 1816, German linguist Franz Bopp (1791–1867) discovered the resemblance of Sanskrit with many Indo-European languages. His most voluminous work *Comparative Grammar of Sanskrit, Zend, Greek, Latin, Lithuanian, Gothic, German, And Slavonic languages* took him over 21 years (1833 to 1852) to complete and aroused unparalleled interest around Europe. In 1897, Latvian poet Rainis with his wife Aspazija (birth name: Johanna Emilija Lizete Rozenberga, 1865–1943) jointly translated Goethe's *Faust* into Latvian and this is a turning point in the Latvian literary and linguistic history since this deeply philosophical literary work required coining of new words and concepts in Latvian language. Rainis had been fascinated

⁹ Daija, P. *Literary History and Popular Enlightenment in Latvian Culture*. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2017, p. 8.

¹⁰ Furst, L. R. *Romanticism in Historical Perspective*. *Comparative Literature Studies*, 5, 1968, pp. 119–120.

¹¹ Chatterji, S. K. *Balts and Aryans in their Indo-European Background*. Simla: Indian Institute of Advanced Study, 1968, p. 61.

¹² Wilhelm, F. *The German Response to Indian Culture*. pp. 395–397.

¹³ Strods, H. "J. G. Herders un latviešu tautasdziesma". Rīga: *Karogs*, No. 6, 01.06.1983, pp. 147–152.

¹⁴ Abrola, N. *Pedagoģiskās vērtības vēdiskajos tekstos – Upaniśādās un to pārantojamība mūsdienu Indijas kultūrvīdē*. University of Latvia. Faculty of Education, Psychology and Art, Department of Education, 2017, p. 4.

and influenced by the grandeur of Goethe's mind, literary, philosophical and scientific works since his college days¹⁵.

2. National awaking in Latvia and India

The period from the end of 19th century to the 1940s was a very complicated time in the history of Latvia, as it had experienced the first national awakening before, and during the time – two revolutions in 1905 and 1917 under the rule of Tsarist Russia, as well as the World War I, until it acquired independence in 1918.

After the long colonial oppression, the processes of national awakening commenced in both countries – India and Latvia, beginning in the middle of the 19th century, regardless of their geographically distant locations. In Latvia, the national awakening was initiated by the elite of intelligentsia at Tērbata University – the burgeois of the eventually formed movement called “New Latvians”. The most renown and active among them were Krišjānis Valdemārs (1825–1891), Juris Alunāns (1832–1864), Atis Kronvalds (1837–1875) and Krišjanis Barons (1835–1923). All had been influenced by the German national movement in 1948, as well as the translations of Latvian folksongs and ideas of nationalism propagated by the German philosopher, theologian, poet and literary critique – Herder, who had come to Riga as a young clergymen in 1764 to work there.

A similar process of national awakening could be observed in India too, as pointed out by Sigma Ankrava¹⁶ and Viktors Ivbulis.¹⁷ The most influential and significant litterateurs included Henry Louis Vivian Derozio (1809–1831) with his sisters Aru (1854–1874) and Toru (1856–1877) Dutt, a philosopher and religious person Swami Vivekananda (birth name:

¹⁵ The Latvian National Library. J. V. Gēte. *Fausts*. 1898 (translated by Aspazija and Rainis). Anotācija, (n.p.), 2015. Available at <https://runa.lnb.lv/63652/> (retrieved 07.11.2018).

¹⁶ Ankrava, S. *Dzeja un politika Indijā. Pirmsneatkarības periods*. Rīga: LU Akadēmiskais apgāds, 2011, pp. 9–20.

¹⁷ Ivbulis, V. *No indiešu civilizācijas vēstures. Kā radusies Indija*. Rīga: Apgāds Zvaigzne ABC, 2017, p. 293.

Naredrandranath Dotto, 1863–1902), brothers Manmohan (1869–1924) and Aurobindo (1872–1950) Ghose, as well as poetess Sarojini Naidu (birth name: Chattopadhyay; 1879–1949) who all contributed to the process of national awaking with their literary works and public activities.¹⁸ Besides them, Viktors Ivbulis also mentions the entrepreneur living in London at that time – Dadhabhai Naoroji (1825–1917) and a religious person Ramakrishna Paramahansa (birth name: Gadadhar Chattopadhyay; 1836–1886), and the last but not the least – Rabindranath Tagore (1861–1941),¹⁹ whose literary works and social activity were recognized not only in India, but far beyond its borders. There certainly were many more persons who contributed to the national awaking of both of the countries, however, due to the limited scope of this article only a few names could be highlighted.

3. Early publications on Sanskrit and Indian literature

To obtain an overview of the repository²⁰ of newspapers published in Latvia since 1810, the search word ‘sanskrits’ was entered, and it showed that the first newspaper record in Latvia mentioning Sanskrit language was published in German language (old orthography) in the newspaper *Rigasche Zeitung* in 1819, which was actually republishing London news.²¹ From 1819 to 1859 altogether fifty-nine newspaper publications in German language (both old and new orthography) are indicated. The very first newspaper publication in Latvian language (old orthography) was

¹⁸ Ankrava, S. *Dzeja un politika Indijā. Pirmsneatkarības periods*. Rīga: LU Akadēmiskais apgāds, 2011, pp. 19–20.

¹⁹ Ivbulis, V. *No indiešu civilizācijas vēstures. Kā radusies Indija*. Rīga: Apgāds Zvaigzne ABC, 2017, pp. 314–369.

²⁰ Latvian National Digital Library. (n.p.), (n.d.), www.periodika.lv (retrieved 10.11.2018).

²¹ London, den 10. December. *Rigasche Zeitung* No. 102. Riga, 20.12.1819. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:/p_003_rzei1819s01n102|article:DIVL45|query:Sanskrit|issueType:P (retrieved 10.11.2018).

published in 1856 in a newspaper *Mahjas weesis* titled “Ihsas ziņņas pahr to, kur Latweeschi cebluschees un kahdi eeraddumi teem bijuschi weccōs laikōs”^{22, 23} This article informs the reader about the similarities of Latvian and Sanskrit languages, as well as a custom of wearing long hair and beard among both the nations: Latvians and Indians. Moreover, it states that the Latvians originated from Asia, the River Ganges region. In addition, the author gives an overview of all the Latvian major and minor ancient pagan deities and their functions, although it is obvious that he or she condemns the pagan traditions and praises the Christian faith. In the time span from 1810 to 1900, 172 newspaper records can be found containing the search word ‘sanskrits’, namely, the topic of the origins of the Latvians and their language was broadly discussed, whereas from 1900 to 1940, the number of articles soared to 601 – both in old and new orthography, while none were found either in Latgalian or English. Only one article applying a search word ‘санскрит’ was found in Russian (old orthography) dedicated to Rabindranath Tagore.

Another newspaper article spotted by the author was published in 1873 in old Latvian orthography, and it informed the readers of Riga city that the Holy Bible was rendered into Sanskrit by German missionary called Wenger in the city of Calcutta (India), who started this work in 1847 and completed it in 1873.²⁴ It is noteworthy to highlight the astounding medley of praising Christian tradition and at the same time diminishing the reminiscence of pagan traditions, and comparison to the pagan traditions in a far, distant country like India. The above-mentioned

²² The translation in English: “Brief notes on the origins of the Latvians and their habits in ancient times”. Translated by the author. Due to the lack of old orthography font, the title has not been typed precisely.

²³ M., F. “*Ihsas ziņņas pahr to, kur Latweeschi cebluschees un kahdi eeraddumi teem bijuschi weccōs laikōs*”, *Mahjas weesis* (6), Riga, 06.08.1856. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2-viewer/view/index-dev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:/p_001_mavi1856n06|article:DIVL26|query:Sanskritu|issueType:P (retrieved 10.11.2018).

²⁴ D. Bihbele pahrelta Sanskrit wallod. *Latviešu Avīzes*, No. 8, 1873. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:/p_001_laav1873n08|article:DIVL159|query:Sanskrit|issueType:P (retrieved 10.11.2018).

number of published articles certainly reflected the incredible interest among the peoples of Latvia despite the dominance of Christian religious community and this could be perfectly explained by two preconditions: the dawn of Romanticism in Latvia fuelled by the movement of national awaking. Perhaps the ambiguous interest in Orient might have been considered a threat to the clergy of well-rooted Christianity, and in particular Lutheran church, which dominated in Latvia. Thus, in 1880, the first book in Old Gothic orthography on the work of German missionary Richard Handmann (1840–1912)²⁵ was published in Latvian, titled *Joga Surapenna Kilkotejas zemidara dzīves gājums un atgriešana*^{26, 27, 28}. The book of 32 pages is a narrative dedicated to the life and ordeals of an Indian zamindar called Yoga Surapenna and the hardship of a missionary to convert a ‘well rooted pagan’ into an obedient Christian devotee. The narrative is a rich source of historical data on the life of Indian people and the methods applied by Handmann to convert as many indigenous people as possible into Christianity, and particularly into Lutheranism, hence, it could be considered as a chronicle. Handmann advocates the doctrine of Christianity as the only saviour from ordeals undergone by Yoga Surapenna, namely, imprisonment. Surapenna’s conversion takes place in three stages: disappointment into his ancestors’ gods followed by conversion into Islam, and finally, after disappointment in Islam, he gets converted into Christianity. The narrator also indirectly reveals that some of his first converts belonged to the lowest classes of social strata,

²⁵ Richard Handmann – a highly prolific German missionary from Leipzig mission with 39 works in 95 publications in 2 languages and 329 library holdings. Available at <http://worldcat.org/identities/lccn-no98064600/> (retrieved 18.11.2018).

²⁶ The translation of title in English. Yoga Surapenna – the course of the life of a zamindar from Kilkoteya and his converting, 1880. (Latv. Sarakstīts no Riht Indijas Trischinopoles ewangeliskas littera tizzibas missionara R. Handmanna; Engl. Written by the East India Trischinopole Lutheric religion missionary R. Handmann).

²⁷ Handmann, R. Translated into Latvian by Blumberg, H. *Joga Surapenna Kilkotejas zemidara dzīves gājums un atgriešana*. Rīga, 1880.

²⁸ Handmann, R. *Iogi Surappen der Zemindar von Kilkotei*. Available at <http://www.worldcat.org/title/iogi-surappen-der-zemindar-von-kilkotei-eine-bekehrungsgeschichte-erzahlt-von-rh-etc/oclc/560205789> (retrieved 18.11.2018).

most likely, outcasts as by converting into Christianity they obtained some human rights – a significant reason to abandon the religion of the forefathers²⁹. Needless to say, the Indians or pagans are depicted in a very controversial manner, firstly, as people belonging to a learned and highly spirited nation, and at the same time, as very shallow persons, emotionally as cold as stone.³⁰

Thus, the narrative of Yoga Surrapenna is preceded only by a handwritten manuscript, in black ink, additions in pencil and black ink, on Sanskrit studies³¹ by a Latvian poet and philologist Jēkabs Lautenbahs-Jūsmiņš (birth name: Jēkabs Lautenbahs, 1847–1928)³². He was also a lecturer, privatdocent and a professor (1878–1918) at the Faculty of History and Philosophy at University of Terbata (contemporary Tartu). Lautenbahs-Jūsmiņš wrote articles on the themes of literature, linguistics, folklore, mythology etc. in Latvian, Russian and German languages. Another book on Sanskrit grammar³³, printed in German language, was discovered by the author of this article in the library of Latvian Roerich Society³⁴.

Then, in 1888, the same year, when Latvian epic *Bearslayer* was completed, the *Hitopadeca*^{35, 36} was published in Germany in Old Gothic orthography – a renowned collection of Indian ‘folk’ wisdom – useful tips, fables, maxims based on ideas reflected in *Panchatantra*^{37, 38} that

²⁹ Handmann, R. Translated into Latvian by Blumberg, H. *Joga Surapenna Kilkotejas zemidara dzīves gājums un atgriešana*. Rīga, 1880, pp. 15–16.

³⁰ Ibid, p. 5.

³¹ Lautenbahs-Jūsmiņš, J. *Anleitung zum Studien der Sanskrit-Sprache*. (n.p.), 187 u.

³² More about life and work of Lautenbahs-Jūsmiņš, J. Available at <http://literatura.lv/autors/Jekabs-Lautenbahs-Jusmins/26319> (retrieved 18.11.2018).

³³ Fick, R. *Praktische Grammatik der Sanskrit-Sprache für den Selbstunterricht*. Wien: A. Hartleben's Verlag, 18 uu.

³⁴ More information about Latvian Roerich Society is available at <http://www.latvijaserihabiedriba.lv/images/RXLVang.htm> (retrieved 18.11.2018).

³⁵ Fritze, L. *Hitopadeça: Ein Indisches Lehrbuch Der Lebensklugheit In Erzählungen Und Sprüchen*. Leipzig: O. Wigand, 1888.

³⁶ In Sanskrit: हितोपदेशः [Hitopadeśa]. IAST transliteration.

³⁷ In Sanskrit: पञ्चतन्त्र [Pañcatantra]. IAST transliteration.

³⁸ More about Pañcatantra. Available at <http://www.oxfordreference.com/view/10.1093/oi/authority.20110810105545695> (retrieved 18.11.2018).

was composed 100–500 B.C. in Sanskrit by an ancient brahmin called Viṣṇuśarman. However, it was received by the Misiņš Library only in 1925, most likely, as a donation from a private collection. It is impossible to trace the exact year when the book reached Latvia.

A few years later, in 1891, Latvian readers were introduced to Indian customs, religious views, virtues, household and culture based on the oldest ancient Indian scripture – the Rigveda – in the article in Latvian language “Indiešu vecākā kultūra un literatūra”³⁹ by Weismaņu Jānis⁴⁰ (1867–1913) which was published in the first nationally oriented periodical containing article collections and titled *Sēta, Daba, Pasaule*⁴¹, released in Jelgava, in the notebook No. 6. The publication of the periodical was realized in the time span from 1860–1893 by Latvian intelligentsia called ‘New Latvians’. The reference to this work is also given in the index of belletrist literature translated into Latvian, which was published in 1902⁴².

There are nine articles in Latvian National Digital Library (www.periodika.lv) covering the time span from 1810–1940 and dedicated to Ancient Indian music, however, the most explicit information on music is given in “Pictorial Music of Fabulous India” by professor of Ancient Indian music Krishna Narain Swami (n.d.)⁴³, whereby Latvian reader is introduced to the history, music instruments and tone system of Ancient Indian music.

Latvian scholars who had dedicated a considerable time to Indology, achieving recognised and well-appreciated results, include a linguist,

³⁹ Translation by the author of this paper in English: *Indian oldest culture and literature*.

⁴⁰ He was also publishing under the pseudonym Pavasaru Jānis.

⁴¹ Apgādājis Alunāns, J. *Sēta, Daba, Pasaule*. Sestā burtnīca. Jelgava: Drukāta pie I. F. Stefenhāgena un dēla, 1891. More information available at http://www.lingvistiskakarte.lv/tag/seta_daba_pasaule (retrieved 19.11.2018).

⁴² Sastādījis Āronu Matiss. *Latviešu tulkotās beletristikas rādītājs*. Rīga: Drukājuši Kalniņš un Deutschman, 1902.

⁴³ Svami, P. K. N. *Teiksmainās indijas gleznainā muzika*. Rīga: *Atpūta* No. 775, 1939. The original orthography of the professor’s name given in the article is retained here.

ethnographer and folklore scholar, professor Pēteris Šmits (1869–1938)⁴⁴ – the first Latvian orientalist who had mastered Chinese, Manchurian, Mongolian and a number of other languages⁴⁵, however, there is no evidence that Šmits had mastered Sanskrit. Yet Šmits had written a comparative research on the mythology of the Balts, Greeks, Romans, Prussians and Indo-Europeans in the book *Baltu Mitoloģija* (1918)⁴⁶ and a number of publications on Oriental languages, Latvian philology and Latvian language, the latter one in collaboration with another great Latvian scholar – linguist and philologist – Jānis Endzelīns (1873–1961)⁴⁷. Endzelīns brought extensive contribution to development of Latvian language, but mainly gained recognition as a world class scientist with his research methods in historic-comparative linguistics.⁴⁸ The connection of Endzelīns with Indology will be more elaborated in the next sections. One cannot miss a social activist and a chief of Lutheran Church in Luga parish, Sankt-Petersburg Gubernia, the Russian Empire – Juris Lecis (sometimes called Lecis, 1860–1935)⁴⁹ who apparently had written quite specifically about such Ancient Indian scriptures as the Rigveda, Atharvaveda, and gives references to Taittiriya-Brahmanam⁵⁰, and even analyses and comparisons of Sanskrit terms and mythological deities with

⁴⁴ More information about Pēteris Šmits is available at <http://garamantas.lv/lv/person/25873/Peteris-Smits> (retrieved 07.12.2018).

⁴⁵ His contemporaries argued that Šmits had mastered 26 languages. Information available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:p_001_burt1928n06|article:DIVL253|query:P%C4%93teri%20%C5%A0mitu%20P%C4%93teri%20%C5%A0mitu|issueType:P (retrieved 19.11.2018).

⁴⁶ Prof. Šmidt, P. *Latviešu mitoloģija*. Maskava: Latviešu Rakstnieku un Mākslinieku Biedriba, 1918, pp. 7–16.

⁴⁷ More about Jānis Endzelīns available at <http://garamantas.lv/lv/person/26246/Janis-Endzelins> (retrieved 07.12.2018).

⁴⁸ Endzelina, N. J. *Par latveeschu prepozicijam*. Austrums (8). Riga, 1897.

⁴⁹ Misāne, A. *Reliģija un latviešu nacionālisms ideju vēsturē Latvijā*. Latvijas Universitāte Vēstures un filozofijas fakultāte: Filozofijas nodaļa, 2016, p. 78. Available at http://dspace.lu.lv/dspace/bitstream/handle/7/34500/298-56364-Misane_Agita_am09480.pdf?sequence=1 (retrieved 08.12.2018).

⁵⁰ Original orthography has been retained.

Latvian counterparts in two of his pamphlets titled *Aryans-Latvians*⁵¹ and *Creed of Ancient Latvians and prettiness of the Soul in Social Life*⁵². However, Agita Misāne also admitted that these articles and a research work did not qualify for publishing elsewhere in scientific journals⁵³, neither there was any evidence that Lecis would have known Sanskrit himself. Most likely, Lecis had reproduced some ideas of German Indologists, whose references he had given, namely, German philosopher and Indologist Paul Jakob Deussen (1845–1919) and a Latvian researcher – A. Winter (n.d.) who had written an article dedicated to one Latvian folksong and the hymn of Rigveda,⁵⁴ and etymological analyses were rather superficial and arbitrary.

Perhaps one of the most remarkable manuscripts discovered by the author in the Misiņš library, is *Commentaries on Avesta and Rigveda* by Kārlis Zalts⁵⁵ (1885–1953) – a mathematician and researcher of folklore. Zalts had been publishing his scientific articles with the real name, as well as pseudonym ‘Zalktis’ since 1906 on themes related to exact sciences, philosophical matters, and also Latvian folklore, specifically focusing on road transportation in ancient Latvia, and horse related research. Therefore, finding the handwritten manuscript in Russian, Latvian and German (old orthography) – written in Kiev from 1907 to 1909 was a great surprise, as it was apparently not exposed to large audiences and certainly remained unpublished. However, this discovery alongside with the article related to Rigveda by Weismaņu Jānis, as well as several other publications in German

⁵¹ Leca, J. *Āreeši – latveeši*. Jelgava: Latviešu etnogrāfijas biedrības izdevums, No. 30, 1914.

⁵² Lecis, J. *Senlatviešu dievticība un dvēseles glītums sadzīvē*. Rīga: Latviešu etnogrāfijas biedrības izdevums, No. 3, 1917.

⁵³ Misāne, A. *Reliģija un latviešu nacionālisms ideju vēsturē Latvijā*. Latvijas Universitāte Vēstures un filozofijas fakultāte, Filozofijas nodaļa, 2016, pp. 77–79.

⁵⁴ Winter, A. *Mein Bruder freit um mich (Grib brālītis mani jemt)*. Mythologischer Versuch über ein lettisches Volkslied und ein Lied des Rig-Veda, Berlin: Verlag von A. Asher & Co, 1897, pp. 172–184. Available at <https://www.digi-hub.de/viewer/image/DE-11-001674327/186/> (retrieved 08.12.2018). Unfortunately, the author of this paper did not succeed to trace more information about Latvian researcher Winter, A.

⁵⁵ More about Kārlis Zalts is available at <http://garamantas.lv/lv/person/26678> (retrieved 19.11.2018).

language, is a clear indication of the profound interest of Latvian scholars and intelligentsia in Indian literatures. The author possesses no evidence on the reasons why the latter manuscript remained unpublished. One can only speculate whether there was a threat of censorship by the tsarist regime of Russian empire or other considerations. Most likely, more studies were conducted by Latvian scholars and intelligentsia that would require an in-depth research. Nevertheless, it might partially explain the interest of the great Latvian poet Rainis in Oriental literatures and philosophies that will be more explicitly elaborated upon in the next section.

4. Latvian poets, writers and translators – the early Indologists from 1900 to 1940

The current section contains an overview of translations of Indian literature into Latvian from 1900 to 1940, as well as a new dimension of Rainis's personality related to Oriental philosophies.

The list and overview of translations of Indian literary works into Latvian was given in the edition of *The History of Latvian Writing* (1934)⁵⁶. Vilis Plūdons (birth name: Vilis Lejnietis; 1874–1940) – a Latvian poet translated *Chudraka*⁵⁷ (*Čudraka*) – the ancient Sanskrit drama in ten acts in 1910⁵⁸, and later it was also staged in the contemporary Latvian National Theatre during the occupation period under the title *Vasantasena*.⁵⁹

⁵⁶ Zeiferts, T. *Latviešu rakstniecības vēsture*. 3. sējums. Rīga: A. Gulbja grāmatu piestuve, 1934, pp. 520–521.

⁵⁷ In Sanskrit: शूद्रक [Śūdraka]. IAST transliteration. Plūdons, V. (translator). *Čudraka*. Original title of the play is In Sanskrit: मृच्छकटिक [Mṛcchakaṭika]. IAST transliteration. In Europe, the work was titled *Vasantasena*.

⁵⁸ Zeiferts, T. *Latviešu rakstniecības vēsture*. 3. sējums. Rīga: A. Gulbja grāmatu piestuve, 1934, pp. 520–521.

⁵⁹ Kārklīš-Zeltmatis, E. *Latviešu teātris okupācijas laikā*. Rīga: Izglītības Ministrijas Mēnešraksts, No. 12, 1938. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2-viewer/view/index-dev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:/p_001_izmm1938n12|article:DIVL153|query:Vasantasena|issueType:P (retrieved 08.12.2018).

Professor of the University of Latvia Aleksandrs Janeks (1891–1970)⁶⁰, the pioneer of colloidal chemistry in Latvia introduced the Latvian reader to the teachings of Buddha – *Buddhas mācības pamati* (1924)⁶¹ and a number of other publications on Buddhism, religion life and culture.⁶²

Teodors Lejas Krūmiņš (1871–1947), a writer and translator, translated *The Beggar Woman* or *The Beggar Girl* (*Indietes stāsti*) in 1921.⁶³

Valts Dāvids (1890–1969), a writer and translator, translated Rabindranath Tagore's (1861–1941) poem "The Crescent Moon" ("Augošs mēness") and one act play *Chitra* (*Ķitra*) – both in 1922.⁶⁴

Jēkabs Janševskis (birth name: Jēkabs Janovskis; 1865–1931), a Latvian teacher, journalist, translator and writer, translated classical Sanskrit writer – Kalidasa's (the 4th–5th century CE) *Shakuntala*⁶⁵ (*Šākuntala*).⁶⁶

A Latvian writer and an art scholar Viktors Eglītis (1877–1945) was also mentioned in the anthology of Latvian written history⁶⁷, indicating that he also had been influenced by Indian Rigveda.

A long section dedicated to the ancient Indian literature, poetry and epic genre giving an overview of the Vedas, Upanishads, epics *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata*, Puranas, Jainism and Buddhism texts, classical Sanskrit and Prakrit poetry, Dravidian literature, as well as Hindu literature of that period represented by several renown Indian authors, for instance, Tagore,

⁶⁰ Alksnis, U., Grosvalds, I. *Profesors Aleksandrs Janeks*. Latvijas Universitātes raksti, 815. sēj.: Zinātņu vēsture un muzejniecība, 2017, pp. 13–22. Available at https://www.lu.lv/fileadmin/user_upload/lu_portal/apgads/izdevumi/LU_Raksti/815/01_Alksnis.pdf <https://doi.org/10.22364/luraksti.zvm.815.03> (retrieved 09.12.2018).

⁶¹ Janeks, A., *Buddhas mācības pamati*. Rīga: Finanšu ministrijas jūrnieceības departamenta izdevums, 1924.

⁶² Alksnis, U., Grosvalds, I. *Profesors Aleksandrs Janeks*. Latvijas Universitātes raksti, 815. sēj.: Zinātņu vēsture un muzejniecība, 2017, p. 21.

⁶³ Zeiferts, T. *Latviešu rakstniecības vēsture*. 3. sējums. Rīga: A. Gulbja grāmatu spiestuve, 1934, pp. 520–521.

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ In Sanskrit: शकुन्तला [Śakuntalā], IAST transliteration.

⁶⁶ Zeiferts, T. *Latviešu rakstniecības vēsture*. 3. sējums. Rīga: A. Gulbja grāmatu spiestuve, 1934, pp. 520–521.

⁶⁷ Ibid., p. 125.

was published in the illustrated almanac *The World History of Writing*⁶⁸. A writer and translator Jānis Veselis (1896–1962)⁶⁹ in 1931 composed a tragedy in three acts *Jumis*⁷⁰ – a dramatic poem that depicts the migration processes of ancient Aryans. 36 actors were involved in 54 roles named after many well-known characters and deities from Latvian and Indian mythology and epic literature, for instance: Sita, Jumis, Naja, Hanumats, Vivasvats, Barata etc.⁷¹ Unfortunately, Veselis did not finish the translation of ancient Indian epic *Mahabharata*.

Another Latvian amateur researcher and a writer who was highly estimated by the contemporaries for his research work on comparative linguistics, mythology and Latvian language history – Voldemārs Leitis⁷² (n.d.), who at his own expense published four books: *Latvian-like Indian Rigveda* (1938)⁷³ – the entire book is permeated with the ideas to raise Latvian nationalism by means of showing its ancient roots; *Latvian Gods in Asia* (1939)⁷⁴ – the mythological deities of Latvia, Egypt, Japan, China and India; *The Master, Cow and a Ploughman* (1939)⁷⁵ – on the etymology of Latvian words; *Blonde or Brunette?: (difference of characters)* (1939) – on

⁶⁸ Egle, R. Upīts, A. *Pasaules rakstniecības vēsture*. 1. grāmata. Rīga: izdevis A. Gulbis, 1930, pp. 16–76.

⁶⁹ More information about Jānis Veselis is available at <http://garamantas.lv/lv/person/25654/Janis-Veselis> (retrieved 09.12.2018).

⁷⁰ *Jumis* – an ancient Latvian deity and a symbol of fertility and wealth, often linked to crop yield. Graphic design of this symbol can be depicted as two crotchets and may look like English letter ‘W’. Available at <http://valoda.aialab.lv/kultura/kultura/oron12.htm> (retrieved 09.12.2018).

⁷¹ Osis, J. *Jāņa Vesēļa traģēd. 3 cēl. ‘Jumis’*. Rīga: Filma un Skatuve, No. 23, 1931. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:p_001_fisk1931n23|article:DIVL215|query:%C4%81rie%C5%A1u%20%C4%81rie%C5%A1u|issueType:P (retrieved 09.12.2018).

⁷² Most likely, Leitis was a president of American Latvian Trade Community who left America for Latvia in July 21, 1920. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:p_001_amea1920n03|article:DIVL71|query:Voldem%C4%81rs%20Leitis|issueType:P (retrieved 25.12.2018).

⁷³ Leitis, V. *Latviskā Indijas Rigveda*. Rīga: Aut. izd., 1938.

⁷⁴ Leitis, V. *Latviešu dievi Āzijā*. Rīga: Aut. izd., 1939.

⁷⁵ Leitis, V. *Kungs, govns un arājs*. Ogrē: Aut. izd., 1939.

anthropometric features of Asian and Latvian people, as well as differences in character traits. A newspaper article, as well as the information acquired during the interview with the respondent⁷⁶ reveals that *Leitis* was also invited to read on his research at the Society of Researchers of Latvia in Antiquity (*Latvijas senatnes pētītāju biedrība*) and he had been working on *Latvian – Aryan dictionary* (*Latviešu – āriešu vārdnīca*)⁷⁷ stating that *Leitis* had found 30 000 terms similar to the ones in the Vedas, whereas another article denominates it *The Historical Dictionary of the Latvian language* (*Latviešu valodas vēsturiskā vārdnīca*) and the number of terms collected by *Leitis* – 25 000,⁷⁸ as well as his works were sent to Theodor Diedrichson – a Latvian scholar working and residing in Beijing, China,⁷⁹ who had given suffice arguments to support *Leitis*'s and professor Šmits's assertions on the matter of resemblance of Latvian binary mythological deity *Jumis* with its counterparts: Avestan *Yima*, Pahlavi *Yimak*, Buddhist and Aryan *Yama* and *Yamī*, Persian *Yim* and *Yimak*, Chinese *Yin* and *Yang*, Japanese *Izanaki* and *Izanami*, and, finally, Egyptian *Osiris* and *Isis*.

Rihards Rudzītis (1898–1960), a poet, philosopher, essayist, translator, a social activist, and a president of Latvian Roerich Society from 1936 to 1940. Rudzītis had studied the classical languages at Terbata University,

⁷⁶ The respondent Valdis Muktupāvels, Dr. art., prof. at the University of Latvia informed about the Latvian-Sanskrit Dictionary, record No. 4618, (retrieved 25.12.2018).

⁷⁷ *Latviešu valoda priekš 4000 gadiem*. Rīga: *Rīts*, No. 103, 1935. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:p_001_rits1935n103|article:DIVL350|query:senatn%C4%93%20Latvie%C5%A1u%20senatnes%20p%C4%93t%C4%ABt%C4%81ju%20biedr%C4%ABbas|issueType:P (retrieved 09.12.2018).

⁷⁸ *Grāmatu galds. Visai intereranta grāmata par Āzijas materiāliem mūsu senovēsturei*. Rīga: *Valdības Vēstnesis*, No. 104, 1939. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/index-dev.html?lang=fr#panel:pp|issue:p_001_wawe1939n104|page:13|issueType:P (retrieved 08.12.2018).

⁷⁹ Diedrichson's detailed response was published in the newspaper *Dzimtenes atskaņas*, No. 4, Tientsin (China): Tientzinas latviešu biedrības literaras sekcijas izdevums, 1939, pp. 43–52. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pp|issue:p_001_dzas1939n04|article:DIVL754|issueType:P (retrieved 25.12.2018).

translations of the Bible in different languages, treatises on Buddhism, Bhagavad-Gita, Theosophical literature and the works by Helen Roerich (1879–1955) and Nicholas Roerich (1874–1947). He had also translated the works by Vivekananda, and the Roerichs Tagore etc. However, among all the translations it is noteworthy to highlight the translation of collected works of Tagore within a time span from 1927 to 1934 in collaboration with Kārlis Egle (1887–1974), a bibliographer, literary historian, a translator. A letter written by Rudzītis to Egle on March 9, 1921⁸⁰ reveals that Egle suggested translating and publishing the collected works of Tagore, an idea Rudzītis accepted with great delight, however, doubted to find funding for it.

Although Rudzītis admired Rainis and even had written him a letter, yet he did not receive the reply from Rainis, and their friendship failed to develop. They met only once in Riga, in 1929. As the body language suggests in the photo (Figure 1), Rudzītis did not feel comfortable in that atmosphere. Moreover, his daughter Gunta Rudzīte admitted that her father was slightly disappointed after meeting Rainis, as he found him too pragmatic.⁸¹ Rudzītis's diary reveals that he felt perplexed and disappointed on the fact Rainis had turned from socialism to individualism. "He is such a singleton that he rather craves friendship". Rudzītis also finds detachment in religious views – not only longing for humanity, but also for transcendence⁸².

A letter sent to Aspazija by Rudzītis on October 7, 1929⁸³ shortly after the death of Rainis allows to discern some new dimensions of Rainis's personality. Despite of the fact Rainis was a lawyer by education and also a politician and public figure, he had believed in the immortality of the soul. In addition, in his letter Rudzītis claimed that although Rainis was a

⁸⁰ A letter is available in Kārlis Egle fund in *Misiņa library*.

⁸¹ The interview with Gunta Rudzīte and Alvilis Hartmanis, registered No. 4614 in the catalogue of ANOH.

⁸² Rudzītis, R. *Dvēseles dziesmas*. Dienasgrāmatas II. daļa 1920.–1930, n.p.: Izdevniecība "Sirds gaisma", 2011, pp. 433–436.

⁸³ Source: Literature and Music Museum (Latvia), inventory No. RTMM-71057 Asp K 75/26.

Figure 1. February 27, 1929 at Riga City Hospital No. 2. Left to right – Rudzītis with Johanna Keģis, Rainis and a nurse Dombrovskā, the last person is unknown.

Source: Literature and Music Museum (Latvia), inventory No. RTMM-43508 (1)-Rainis.

very religious person, yet did not belong to any church. Perhaps the most illustrative was epistolary communication in the time span from 1911 to 1915 between Rainis and someone called Ance Rožkalne (birth name: Ripa; n.d.) residing in Dresden, Germany. It reveals that Rainis had studied Theosophical literature, Bhagavad-Gīta etc. In total, Rainis had received 28 postcards⁸⁴ (see Figure 2).

⁸⁴ Source: Literature and Music Museum (Latvia), Rainis's fund, No. Rai K 163/1-28

Figure 2. A letter from Ance Rožkalne sent from Dresden on January 18, 1911.

Deciphered in modern Latvian language by Gundega Grīnuma.

Source: Literature and Music Museum (Latvia),
inventory No. RTMM-120339 (1)-Rainis.

Rainis with his wife, Aspazija, had an extensive library that contained the books from the variety of spheres and all that is an evidence of the vast spectrum of interests and that all certainly had served in the construction of the versatile genius of Rainis. The number of books related to the fields of philosophy, psychology, ethics and religion reach the count of 230.⁸⁵ Among many of the authors and realms that had handwritten notes made by Rainis one can mention the issues of Theosophy Society, Helena Blavatsky on Indian mysticism, ancient Egyptian religion, works on Plato, the Bible and Christianity, Occultism by Emma Balodis⁸⁶, Spiritism, Bhagavad-Gita, Ancient mystery religions and Christianity,

⁸⁵ Source: Literature and Music Museum (Latvia).

⁸⁶ Emma Balodis – a pseudonym of Aleksandrs Balodis (1897–1961), he was a Latvian officer, officer at intelligence service, parapsychologist and a writer, the founder of Latvian society of Cosmosophy. Married to Emma Apre.

Raja Yoga⁸⁷, Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals by Immanuel Kant (1724–1804), Lao-tse, on Talmud etc.

The fact that Rainis had studied Theosophical, Indian literature, Buddhism and showed interest in yoga had been already discussed by Sigma Ankrava⁸⁸, and Viktors Ivbulis in series of articles in a magazine *Karogs* (1988).⁸⁹ The Oriental influence on Rainis's literary works and poetry has also been highlighted by Suniti Kumar Chatterji (1890–1977) in his book *Balts and Aryans* where he finds influence of Karma-Yoga, Bhagavad-Gita and Vedanta philosophy on Rainis's poetry, for instance, a poem "Work and Joy" ("Darbs un prieks") and "The End and the Beginning" ("Gals un sākums")⁹⁰. Furthermore, Kaspars Kļaviņš adds his findings of Sufi ideas being perceived by Rainis through Goethe's works – that all resulted in a fusion of Western and Eastern philosophies⁹¹ that is all-pervasive in the collection of poems *Fire and Night* (*Uguns un nakts*), and alongside the conception of immortality and mythological symbols: solar and lunar, as well the mythological elements of Latvian folk songs are all depicted in the collection of poems *Ave sol*. For example:

*Saulei jāiet lielā gaitā,
Gaisa gali nosarkuši.
Saule taisa ceļā ģērbus:*

*Savus sartos zāda svārkus
Novēdina vakarblāzmā;
Uzvelk jaunu, baltu kreklu,
Melno noiet jūras viļņos. –*

⁸⁷ In-depth studies of *Raja Yoga* by Rainis was indicated by one of the respondents – Jānis Ziemeļis, record No. 4615 in the catalogue of ANOH.

⁸⁸ Ankrava, S. Eastern Dimension in the Representation of Latvian Identity at the Beginning of Latvian Literature and Now. University of Latvia, Scholarly Papers, Vol. 779, Oriental Studies, 2012, pp. 39–52.

⁸⁹ Ivbulis, V. Sasaukšanās pāri kontinentiem. Rīga: Žurnāls *Karogs*, No. 9, 01.09.1988, pp. 162–168.

⁹⁰ Chatterji, S. K. *Balts and Aryans in their Indo-European Background*. Simla: Indian Institute of Advanced Study, 1968, pp. 173–174.

⁹¹ Kļaviņš, K. *Savienotie trauki*. Rīga: LU Akadēmiskais apgāds, 2018, pp. 175–187.

*Aizbrauc saule zelta ratos
 Vīnu dzert uz sudrabkalnu;
 Rokā tura dīvus kausus,
 Labā baltu, kreisā zaļu.
 Labā – ledus sniega putām,
 Kreisā – salda lapu sula:
 Nāvi dzert, lai atkal celtos* (in Latvian)⁹².

Although at a first glance, it may seem that Rainis in parallel to his studies of established religious practices and philosophies had also immersed into the lore of mysticism and occultism, it is not quite so, as he had a vast collection of newspaper cuttings on the topics related to philosophers' views on cosmogony, science, pragmatic future prophecies, for instance, an article on "Edison's views on the future of the mankind"⁹³, the article "Modern magic",⁹⁴ unmasking all these occult sciences and spiritism with contemporary science. All in all, this collection of articles unfolds a very pragmatic and well-educated person, however, at the same time, a romantic philosopher contemplating on the cosmogonic ontology at the dawn of the civilization epistemology of the human existence, a day-dreamer envisioning a beautiful future of the mankind.

5. Societies, organizations and their activities propagating Indic sciences in pre-World War II Latvia

In the period preceding World War II, despite the complicated geopolitical situation in the country, a number of societies and organizations were formed, which apparently collaborated at some cross-points of their ideologies propagated. A vast collection of historiographic material of yoga

⁹² Rainis, J. Kopotie raksti 30 sējumos. 2. sējums. *Ave sol*. Rīga: Izdevniecība "Zinātne", 1977, p. 56.

⁹³ Source: Literature and Music Museum (Latvia), inventory No. RTMM-1231708 Rai J 104/1.

⁹⁴ Source: Literature and Music Museum (Latvia), inventory No. RTMM-28438/3 Rai I 102/3.

movement in Latvia has been investigated by Solveiga Krūmiņa-Koņkova⁹⁵ as well as gathered by an ardent Latvian yoga history activist – Dzintars Vilnis Korns⁹⁶, therefore in this section only a list of the most influential societies with their leaders and their main area of function will be given in a chronological order, exclusively new facts will be given explicitly based on the records in the journals of meetings inter alia archive records.

In the journals of Herder's Institute in Riga (established on September 7, 1921)⁹⁷, one can find a very interesting handwritten table of weekly lesson schedule in German language that clearly displays a particular lesson of Sanskrit texts scheduled on Tuesday afternoon, and the lecturer is Endzelīns⁹⁸, despite of the fact that nobody by the name of Endzelins was found after a close study of the sections that display the names of educators' personnel at the institute⁹⁹.

The Society of Parapsychology (*Parapsīcholoģijas biedrība*) was established in Riga in 1925¹⁰⁰ by Emma Apare and 4 more persons. The main goals set by this society were to explore different psychological phenomena and Oriental metaphysics. However, later on the society changed its name to “The Centre of Yoga Sciences in Latvia”, its chairperson was Harijs Dikmanis (1895–1979), Jānis Veselis (n.d.; a cousin of a writer with the same name). Dikmanis knew Sanskrit and was learning Hindi. The main, but not the only goal of this society was to propagate

⁹⁵ Krūmiņa-Koņkova, S. A glimpse into the history of yoga movement in Latvia. *Reliģiski-filozofiski raksti XVII*. Latvijas Universitātes aģentūra Filozofijas un socioloģijas institūts, 2014, pp. 153–188.

⁹⁶ The interview with Dzintars Vilnis Korns, registered No. 4620 in the catalogue of ANOH.

⁹⁷ N. A. Herdera institūts audzina lojālus Latvijas pilsoņus. *Rīga: Jaunākās Ziņas*, No. 224, 1939. Available at http://www.periodika.lv/periodika2viewer/view/indexdev.html?lang=fr#panel:pa|issue:p_001_jazi1939n224|article:DIVL357|issueType:P (retrieved 30.12.2018).

⁹⁸ LSHA Fund No. 4772, entry No. 1, 1920–1940, p. 73.

⁹⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 88–92.

¹⁰⁰ Krūmiņa-Koņkova, S. A glimpse into the history of yoga movement in Latvia. *Reliģiski-filozofiski raksti XVII*. Latvijas Universitātes aģentūra Filozofijas un socioloģijas institūts, 2014, p. 154.

yoga as a new and alternative way to obtain physical and mental health¹⁰¹ (see Figure 3).

Latvijas Parapsicholoģijas Biedrība
 1. februārī 1931. g. pl. 16, Rīgas Namīpašn.
 B-bas zālē, Brīvības bulvārī 2-4.

Rabindranata Tagores instituta lektors

indietis

Lakšmisvars Sinha
 noturēs priekšlasījumu par sekošu tematu

INDIJA, (turpinājums)

~~Latvijas Parapsicholoģijas Biedrība~~

kulturas un reliģijas problema.

Uz publikas vēlēšanos lektors dos arī sīkākus paskaidrojumus par Rabindranata Tagores un Mahatma Gandhi darbību, kā arī atbildēs uz uzstādītiem jautājumiem.

Priekšlasījumu tulkos latviski.

Ieejas maksa Biedriem, skolniekiem un kareivjiem Ls 0,50, nebiec. Ls 1.-

Figure 3. A poster inviting to attend the sequel lecture “On India, Cultural and Religious Problem” by Lakšmisvar Sinh (Original name: *Laxmiswar Singha*), organized by the Society of Parapsychology.
 Source: The Misiņš Library, Kārlis Egle fund.

¹⁰¹ Krumina-Konkova, S. A glimpse into the history of yoga movement in Latvia. *Reliģiski-filozofiski raksti XVII*. Latvijas Universitātes aģentūra Filozofijas un socioloģijas institūts, 2014, pp. 153–188.

Latvian Society of Vegetarians (*Latvijas Veģetāriešu biedrība*) was established on August 31, 1927¹⁰². Its main objectives are to propagate ideology and practical vegetarianism, to conduct scientific studies of vegetarianisms, to combat all forms of cruelty etc. Among the leaders of the society one can mention doctor Epllē (n.d.), doctor homeopath Haralds Lūkins (1906–1991), and doctor Augusts Vilis Kļaviņš (n.d.). On January 21, 1933, the society decided to arrange discussion evenings on “Ethical Principles of Vegetarianism”, the speakers were Dr. Kļaviņš (n.d.) and Dīkmanis, whereas L. Birnbaum (n.d.) would be reading his report in February on “Vegetarian Dishes of Ancient Latvians”. In the same year, on April 1 events are organized to celebrate Mother’s Day in collaboration with Latvian Anti-Nicotine Society. Rudzītis is also invited to give an open lecture on his essay “Mother’s Mission” (*Mātes misija*)¹⁰³. Later, on December 2, 1933, the board decided to create a three-level program that would investigate the following points: 1) to establish an ideology of life reform; 2) to record individual observations regarding vegetarian diet; 3) to investigate diabetes and propagate a diet based on individual’s character, body type, health condition and occupation¹⁰⁴. Although there are no direct indications of applying Ayurveda methods, yet these attempts show indirectly how they might have been perceived through teachings incorporated in yoga philosophy. At the same time, the records majorly reveal dissemination of the dietary recommendations developed by the Swiss physician at the time – Maximilian Bircher-Brenner (1867–1939)¹⁰⁵.

¹⁰² The Articles of “The Society of Vegetarians” on August 31, 1927. LSHA Fund No. 2479, The 1st entry, No. 1, 1927–1940. There is another copy of Articles in German language.

¹⁰³ LSHA Fund No. 2479, 1st entry, No. 1, 1927–1940, meeting minutes No. 5, April 1, 1933.

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*, meeting minutes No. 15, December 2, 1933.

¹⁰⁵ Wolf, E. A new way of living: Maximilian Bircher-Benner (1867–1939). *At the cutting edge. Swiss Pioneers in Science and Medicine*, No. 71, (n.p.): *Karger Gazette*, 2010, pp. 11–12, DOI: 10.5167/uzh-40410. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271699495_A_new_way_of_living_Maximilian_Bircher-Benner_1867-1939 (retrieved 30.12.2018).

Memories reflected by Lūkins's son, Indars Lūkins, reveal that his father received herbal medicine from Tibet sent by Roerich family¹⁰⁶.

Latvian Anthroposophical Society (*Latvijas antroposofiskā biedrība*) was established in Riga on July 3, 1929 by fifteen members, and its first chairperson was doctor Arthur Weaber (n.d.), the second – Woldemar Fridrichson (n.d.)¹⁰⁷. The society embraced and disseminated the ideology of Rudolf Joseph Lorenz Steiner (1861–1925) and Carl Unger (1878–1929). The number of their followers reached 45 by 1939¹⁰⁸.

Latvian Roerich Society (*Latvijas Rēriha biedrība*) was officially established on October 13, 1930 by doctor Fēlikss Lūkins, however, the ideas of Roerich were initiated by Vladimirs Šibajevs (1898–1975)¹⁰⁹ who had met Nikolay and Helen Roerich in London in 1920¹¹⁰.

The aforementioned Emma Apare-Balodis's husband Aleksandrs Balodis became the first chairpersons of the Society of Latvian Spiritual Sciences (*Latvijas spiritisko zinātņu biedrība*), established on December 24, 1930, which both of them temporarily left in 1933 to re-join again, and then, along with other Russian and German activists established the Society for Promoting Cosmosophic Sciences in Latvia (*Kosmosofijas zinātņu veicināšanas biedrība Latvijā*) on December 19, 1933¹¹¹.

Vegetarian Consumer-Producer Society (*Veģetarais patērētāju-ražotāju kooperatīvs "Laikmets"*) was established on March 22, 1934 by Kārlis Stūre (n.d.), Jānis Missiņš (n.d.), Klements Vaičulenas (n.d.), Anna Brūvelis (n.d.), Katrīna Draudzīņš (n.d.), Lavīze Olga Missiņš (n.d.), Eiženija Fricbergs (n.d.), Aleksejs Rencis (n.d.), Rihards Rudzītis. Soon

¹⁰⁶ Lūkins, I. *Lūkiniem – 100*. Rīga: 2006. Available at <http://www.mezaparks.eu/2007/05/lkiniem-100.html> (retrieved 29.12.2018).

¹⁰⁷ LSHA Fund No. 2910, entry No. 1, case No. 1 (1929–1939), pp. 1–3.

¹⁰⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 23.

¹⁰⁹ Latvian Roerich Society. Available at <http://www.latvijasrerihabiedriba.lv/images/RXLVlat.htm> (retrieved 30.12.2018).

¹¹⁰ The interview with Gunta Rudzīte and Alvilis Hartmanis, registered No. 4614 in the catalogue of ANOH.

¹¹¹ In greater detail the activities described in: Krumina-Konkova, S. A glimpse into the history of yoga movement in Latvia. *Reliģiski-filozofiski raksti XVII*. Latvijas Universitātes aģentūra Filozofijas un socioloģijas institūts, 2014, pp. 155–161.

the number of members reached 27.¹¹² The main aims of the society were to supply consumers with genuine foodstuff of full nutritional value, harmless for health, and provide other consumables. The society neither sold nor produced meat nor meat products, nor fish and fish products¹¹³. In 1935, doctor Fēlikss Lūkins also joined this society. A remarkable fact to mention is that many members of the society were simultaneously engaged in the activities of Latvian Roerich Society.

Conclusion

It should be noted that the interest in Indology firstly arose in France owing to translations of Upanishads by Duperron, further blossoming in the care of German linguists, philosophers and writers: Bopp, Schlegel brothers, Schopenhauer, Goethe and Herder. However, the tide of Indology through Europe was possible owing to the age of Romanticism invoked by English poet Young and later on overtaken by Germans and, in particular, the French philosopher Rousseau, whose disciple was Herder – a German who arouse interest among the Latvian and German intelligentsia to explore the ancient Latvian culture and traditions by collecting Latvian folksongs. The remarkable reciprocal interaction and influence was established between Goethe and Herder – the shared interest of Indian philosophy and Latvian culture and traditions, and later on through Goethe's literary works irrefutable influence upon Rainis's views and literary work. Many of Rainis's contemporaries were also deeply touched and fascinated by Indian literature, philosophy, culture and yoga teachings, to the extent that several societies were established to disseminate and proliferate the ideology and doctrines rooting in the sacred texts of India. Apart from the wave of Romanticism and discovery of the family of Indo-European languages, among which Lithuanian as the closest sister of Latvian was admitted to be the nearest linguistically to Sanskrit, it was also a geopolitical situation that drew together the two nations standing, so far away geographically.

¹¹² LSHA Fund No. 4698, entry No. 1, (years 1934–1937), articles, p. 13.

¹¹³ *Ibid.*, pp. 1–7.

It is evident that the lively interest in Indian culture was also strengthened by a visit of a professor of Ancient Indian music – Krishna Narain Swami. To sum it up, the influence of Indian culture onto Latvian intelligentsia and culture life cannot be underestimated, and therefore it requires further and more profound studies.

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